

CLASSIFICATION OF WORDS IN UZBEK AND ENGLISH**Ruziyeva Gavhar Farhodovna***An English teacher of school 18**In Navbahor district, Navoiy region*

Annotation: This article is about word formation of compound nouns in English and Uzbek languages. In this article we try to explain similarities and dissimilarities of forming Compound nouns in both languages. This is one of the reasons of learning compounds in these languages.

Key words: Compound words, classification of compounds, word formation, derivative words, components, word stem.

In contrast to word formation, word stems are mainly used as a building material in word addition. As a result of word formation and word attachment, new compound words are formed. They are formed by adding affixes to a whole compound word. (blue-eyed, dress-maker). But, nevertheless, the process of making such words is done, first of all, by adding cores. (blue + eye = blue-eyed, dress + make = dressmaker). So here the core becomes the main word-forming element of the compound word. In some cases, it is more difficult to determine the nature of the construction of compound words. (compare, for example, first nighter - coming to the theater premiere, out-of-towner - living out of town, to weekend - spending the weekend). These help to conduct word formation analysis. Regardless of their morphological structure, such new structures fall into the category of compound words. Thus, compounds like first nighter, out-of-towner are derivative words (first-night + land, out-of-town + land): 1) core + base; 2) core + core + base; 3) stem + stem, i.e. a compound verb from a compound noun is made by conversion. Hence, in terms of morphological structure, not all compound words are formed by word addition. The most common models of compound words in modern English word formation are as follows: adj. + n + ed. (loud -voiced - loud + voice + ed; long-

legged - long + legg + ed); n + v + ing (hand clapping - hand + clap + ing); n + v + er (party-giver - party + give + er). In the formation of a compound word, the process of distinguishing the properties of an object or event is taken into account, while the compound word determines whether words such as artificial words belong to a specific semantic group. The second component is determining the meaning of the word covered. compare: for example, stone-covered (street), mist-covered (town), napkin-covered (table). In these given examples, the first component of compound words clarifies the property of the whole word in the transformation into a compound adjective, along with the identification of the word covered by the noun. In compound word formation, the definition of its meanings may be specific not only to the second component but also to the first component, for example, in some compound nouns of the n + n type, the first component may define the second. For example: compare the sequence of compound words with the word flower: (see Figure 1.1):

Figure 1.1 a series of compound words that come with the word flower As can be seen from the picture above, the first component “flower” defines the exhibition, pot, shop t, etc. in the second component. In such cases, the identification of character traits depends on the semantic sequence of the word. The same compound nouns can be identified by showing the sign of the second component separately when it comes to another semantic sequence. For example: the second component

in the word flower-show may represent similar properties in another semantic row. Compare: dog show, book show, furniture show, car show and so on. Therefore, some of the above definitions cannot fully express the concept of a compound word. In addition, the idea that complex words consist of components with independent meanings cannot be applied to complex words in the Uzbek language. This is due to the fact that one or all components of double and repeated words in Uzbek, such as nest-nobud, meva-cheva, apak-chapak, as well as compound words such as hardamkhayol, harkim, sharsharak, consist of elements or metaphors that cannot be used independently.

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